

Characteristics of Beef Cattle Breeders in Merak Hamlet who Utilize Natural Resources in the Baluran National Park

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ABSTRACT: Study this aim for analyzes characteristics breeder to utilization resource nature in the area park national smear. A study was carried out in Merak Hamlet from March to August 2023 against beef cattle breeders. The research methods used are descriptive qualitative through survey field and interviews with breeder cow cut Merak Hamlet. Characteristic results show that beef cattle breeders cut hamlet peacocks aged (>39 years) and included category age productive with low background education, namely (school base). Experience raising cow broilers for quite a long time, namely >20 years. The main livelihood is the worker's family (raising livestock). Ownership of land from land is narrow, non-rice field farming. In conclusion, characteristics of beef cattle breeder, cow broiler, hamlet peacock, including category breeder productive ones who do not need other people's labor, the consequences often activity illegal grazing and utilization has nature in the Baluran National Park area.

KEYWORDS: Characteristics Breeders, Merak Hamlet, Resources Natural

INTRODUCTION

Characteristics breeder is built based on behavioral, psychographic, and demographic elements. Demographics is one of the frequent variables used to determine the ability to communicate and choose related media closely with sources of information. Factors demographic are age, income, education, experience, and cosmopolitan. (Indey et al., 2021) . Temporary characteristics of psychology cover motivation and needs for achievement. (Fauziyah et al., 2015) .

After reaching age 55 or 60 years, the ability to learn and experience more reduce (Fauziyah et al., 2015) . This matter means that age influences the competence and performance of the breeder. Education is one supporting factor for success on a small business scale, with the assumption that the higher the level of education is, the greater the knowledge of managing a business. An adequate level of education is essential for entrepreneurship, especially in guarding continuity efforts and overcoming problems encountered. Informal education (counseling/training) can make it easier for breeders to accept information And increase competence. The connection between competence entrepreneurship with characteristics of breeding cow milk and effort his livestock. Training programs need to be designed and provided to improve the competence of breeders.

Merak Hamlet is one of the hamlets from Sumberwaru Village in the Baluran National Park area, Regency Situbondo, a utilization zone area. The majority of people in Merak Hamlet Work as breeders. Population The Peacock community is 700-800 people, with a population of around 2,600 heads. Merak Hamlet, Sumberwaru Village, District Banyuputih, is one of the areas in the Regency Part of Situbondo. Big, its inhabitants are breeder cows, and the broiler does inside activities in nature, with some on the coast of the region. Generally, breeders in this area utilize nature as a source of livelihood (like wood roast, grass, and spices). Apart from that, some public still use the land around the house for planted vegetation and a hanging economy to source power in the area. The existence of society within nor around the Area Park National is not inseparable from managing the ecosystem forest. The public must participate in the effort to preserve Park National's environment. Narsuka et al., (2009) Explain that development cannot be accomplished without the role of the individual and society, so everyone has rights and obligations to be involved in frame management environment life and to reach development.

Development business cattle cow influenced by characteristics of the breeder. The ability of breeders to manage business livestock will affect cattle productivity. The livestock business will develop if the breeder endeavors to change its methods and grow its characteristics with knowledge related to practical matters with the business farms. Valuable knowledge can be obtained from non-formal education, obtaining information from various sources, utilizing multiple media, expanding experience, and making creative,

innovative, and brave decisions based on standard rules. Key success business farm determined the ability of the perpetrator business To absorb existing information. Information is an essential factor in the enriching knowledge breeder. (Indey et al., 2021) . Study This was done To analyze the characteristics of breeders and the utilization of resource nature in the Baluran National Park area.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study this was implemented in March of August 2023 in Merak Hamlet, Baluran National Park Area. It was a focused study, i.e., breeder cow broiler in Merak Hamlet. Merak Hamlet was selected as a place of study because it has a population of lots of livestock of around 2,600 heads. Besides that, Hamlet's peacock population breeder is big enough with almost all the same characteristics. Farmers in the village peacock nearly daily illegally grazing thousands of tails in the Baluran National Park area.

Research methods used , i.e., method, descriptive, supported qualitative with quantitative data. A descriptive study describes the object under study through sample data or the existence of the population (Sugiyono, 2020). Retrieval technique sample study This uses the purposive sampling technique, which is A technique that takes a sample from a population based on specific criteria. The criteria used can be based on evaluation-specific or quota-specific. Plested et al. (2006) stated that the key respondents are individuals who know society (no must leader or make policy), are involved in the affairs of society, and see the problem. Data collection techniques used a literature study method, direct observation, and interviews with the breeder. Analysis of characteristic data observed by breeders in the study This can be known through age, education level, experience raising livestock, type of work, and cultivated land area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics Breeder cow using broilers resource natural Merak hamlet is presented as a table (tabulation) that includes age, experience raising, level of education, eyes livelihood, and land ownership.

Age	Amount	Percent (%)
< 19 years old	0	0%
19-39	0	0%
> 39 years	8	100.00%
Amount	8	100.00%
Last Education Level	Amount	Percent (%)
No school	1	12.50%
Elementary school	4	50.00%
School Intermediate	3	37.50%
Amount	8	100%
Experience Breeding	Amount	Percent (%)
>11 years	1	12.50%
11-20 years old	2	25.00%
>20 years	5	62.50%
Amount	8	100%
Livelihood	Amount	Percent (%)
Worker family	5	62.50%
Workers / Employees / Employees	3	37.50%
Amount	8	100.00%
Land Ownership	Amount	Percent (%)
Paddy agricultural land	0	0%
Non-rice field agricultural land	8	100.00%
Land isn't it agriculture	0	0%
Amount	8	100%

Source: processed primary data (2023)

Age

The nature of Resource utilization by most Merak Hamlet breeders is age > 39 (100 percent). The category of breeder is age-productive. Peacock Hamlet breeders are taking advantage of the work carried out by productive groups. His height amount, benefits, and resource nature included in the group age productive indicates that there are limitations in the field capable work that gives income adequate for Peacock Hamlet breeders. So, the result is that the utilization of resources in TNB becomes a possible alternative to additional income.

Indey et al., (2021) Stated that the age between 30 and 60 is the age of productivity. Thereby, it can be concluded that the breeder is physically energetic and robust enough to manage the Alone business. After reaching age 55 or 60, the more ability to learn and experience. This matter means that age influences the competence and performance of the breeder. A farmer/breeder is expected to be capable of doing something activity optimally at age productive. Increasingly, breeders will influence the decline in the productivity of farm cow broilers. Another related thing is the ability to adopt innovation. Already, a breeder old will be slow in applying innovations development cow broiler. This matter is affected by the reduction of physical and mental strength. This is for fast responsiveness to every innovation farm. Research result Efu & Simamora (2021) Show characteristics of age, education, and experience breeder cow broiler influence on implementation innovation insemination artificial.

Level of education

Haryani & Rijanta (2019) State that education significantly determines farmers' competence level in doing activity agriculture. Some breeders in Merak Hamlet's extensive background behind low education (Primary School) was 62 %. The final breeder's education level is generally classified as low, i.e., school-based. This matter is in line with the results of the study. Indey et al., (2021) It was reported that the level of education of breeder goats in Hargotirto Village Kulon Progo Regency is generally low, and they are school-based.

The low level of education results in low Skills. For entering the field market, work generally impacts the narrowness of the field possible work they get. However, looking for natural resources requires a level of education or skills, so becoming a benefit of nature in Baluran National Park is the choice they make to save their lives.

The breeder's education level will impact the ability to develop a business cow broiler. The level of education is extended, and the breeder undertakes advanced formal education. With a higher level of education, somebody will form mature thoughts and behaviors as well as the ability to make decisions. Therefore, the education level impacts the breeder's ability to manage a business cow broiler. (Efu & Simamora, 2021) .

Experience Breeding

The activity of raising cow broilers has been carried out by the people of Merak Hamlet for more than 20 years. The length of experience increases the nature of hereditary. This signifies that the activity of raising cow broilers is still growing and being sought after by the people of Merak Hamlet. Azizah et al., (2023) Experience business farm breeder by 30%, i.e., between 10-20 years, shows that many breeders with experience cultivating business cow cut.

Peacock Hamlet Breeders have Enough experience in looking after cattle cows. There are indications that knowledge and skills in breeding and management maintenance of livestock farmers are good because of their experience farming for quite a long time. According to Indey et al., (2021) Experience can determine the level of maturity and technique, which means Skills in performing duties. Knowledge of managing a farm will increase along with experience raising livestock. Long-term farming gives knowledge and skills based on experience raising livestock. Skills are determined by education, knowledge, and expertise.

Livelihood

Part of the people of Merak Hamlet earn a living as a working family (62.50%) consisting of farmers and businesses in small areas managed by the head family (primarily husbands). Breeders are active people, and their days only focused on livestock. The breeder is the person who owns and manages the land. Good That land yourself, land owned by nor land cultivated For look after his livestock.

Work is a purposeful effort to get income and determine factor level success for somebody in their career. Yes, some people choose to become government employees, and some prefer to be self-employed. (Indey et al., 2021) . Maintenance of cattle cow works as savings and interests custom customs. Function cattle as savings aim to prepare cost-effective education for children in the future. Thereby, the sale of cattle cow will done at the time needed For finance education. Apart from that, livestock cows will also be used

in custom customs such as wedding dowry and resource meat at celebrations. This matter shows that raising cows is a business side that promises and delivers significant contributions to income. (Indey et al., 2021) .

Land Ownership

Peacock Hamlet Breeders ownership of the land, including land non-rice farming. Agricultural land, not rice fields. All land agriculture besides rice fields, consisting of from tegal / garden, field/huma, plantation people, forestry people, ponds/debit/ponds/ponds, cages/fields grazing/feeding livestock, temporary land No cultivated, and land agriculture not other rice fields. At the same time, non-agricultural land is designated land for made-place business/activity besides business from field agriculture.

Owned land breeder around 3 ha. Widyarningsih et al., (2019)) stated that the public is motivated to manage land naturally because the results from gardens owned by people feel there is not enough to satisfy the family's needs. Society around Kerinci National Park (TN) does the same. Seblat (TANKS), due to limited land agriculture, uses land TNKS nature to earn additional income.

CONCLUSION

Characteristics Peacock Hamlet Breeders against benefit resource Baluran National Park nature that is age breeder are of age productive (>39 years). Hence, No need for power. Work ladi. However, the Education level is relatively low (Primary School). Experience raising more than > 20 years indicates that knowledge and skills in breeding and management maintenance livestock farmer the better Because own experience farming for quite a long time. Most work the central public hamlet peacock, the worker family (breeder). Ownership of narrow non-rice field land with a large population of cattle, which Lots cause they do illegal grazing and, at the same time, take advantage of the natural other For added income.

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